

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF ECOLOGY IN THE MODERN LIFE OF MANKIND

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Abstract

Anthropogenic changes in the world's landscapes, the complexity and expansion of international economic relations have led to the strengthening of the interaction of mankind with the environment and the increase of the anthropogenic burden on the human condition. It is of special interest to study the interaction of ecological science with other sciences, in accordance with the requirements of modern era, as well as the growing popularity of ecological science in our modern life. Thus, the formation of ecology as a science, the in-depth study of the history of the evolution of this science is considered one of the actual issues of our time. In our world, which is full of contradictions, ecological science, like other sciences, has its own roots and history.

Keywords: Ecology, philosophical thinking, natural resources, nature protection, the living world, evolution.

Introduction. Ecology was formed within the framework of the philosophical worldview of human society. Logically, the development of ecological science was influenced by the generalized dialectical ideas of philosophical knowledge. In the history of ancient philosophical thought, the dialectical approaches between "space-man" played an important role in the genesis of ecological science.

As a result of the logical connection of philosophical thinking with ecological scientific thinking, the ancient philosopher "ecologists" put forward different ideas about the quantitative and qualitative changes in the material world.

Ancient "ecologists" raised the issue of "space-man-space". This led to the dialectical development of ecological scientific ideas and the emergence of scientific directions in the following periods.

BC in the 5th and 4th centuries, Plato (427-347) put forward valuable ideas and measures to protect the Attica hills in southeastern Greece from soil erosion and to maintain their water resources, soil fertility, to regulate population settlement.

BC in the third century, the ancient Indian king Ashoka (268-232 BC) issued an edict forbidding the killing of young and strangled animals for up to six months. In ancient times, measures were taken to protect water sources, ancient settlement caves, valuable trees, and areas rich in wildlife in Central Asia, the Mediterranean countries, and the Caucasus.

In different historical periods, ecological views in ancient Rome and Greece were reflected in the scientific works of philosophers working in the field of natural sciences. In the 18th century, valuable ecological observations found in the works of great philosophers such as K. Linnaeus, J. Barfon, P.S. Pallas, and I.I. Lipeychi were reflected in botany and zoology. In 1273, England passed a law banning air pollution, and 30 years later one of the violators was executed in London. Beginning in the 11th and 12th centuries, a number of practical measures were taken to prevent pollution of various water sources and air in Western European countries. Founded in France in the 14th century, a special enterprise called "Waters and Forests" was responsible for the efficient use and protection of water

and forest resources. During the reigns of King Charles the Great of France (742-814) and King Wilhelm of England (1027-1087), those who cut down forests and killed wild animals were severely punished.

The degradation of the biological world as a result of anthropogenic and technogenic impacts annually leads to the destruction of a large number of plant and animal species, creating "dead zones" in a particular territory. Currently, the environment is so polluted that the ecological crisis in local areas continues to threaten the lives of living beings and people, and in recent years, this process has accelerated. If this situation persists in the biosphere, serious threats to the life of living beings and humans may arise in the future.

Brief historiography. At present, the influence of the human element on the ecosystem has increased dramatically, as man-made technology, used as a means of influencing nature, has become almost uncontrollable and anarchic, acquiring a status almost independent of man. As a result, global problems arise that are of great concern to mankind and are becoming more and more intractable, and it is difficult to say that they will not continue. The direction and maintenance of the balance formed in nature depend on the economic activity of man, because this balance determines the development of nature by its own laws.

Ecological crisis is not only the pollution of air, water, soil and nutrients. Transformation and, in some cases, degradation of natural ecosystems as a result of anthropogenic impact lead to disruption of the biogeochemical cycle and, ultimately, environmental sustainability. This is reflected not only in the negative changes in the environment, but also in the structure of the human genome. The steady increase in hereditary diseases in all countries of the world is due to genetic changes. This is primarily due to the fact that the health of the population is directly dependent on environmental hazards. At the same time, it should be noted that in a number of cases, changes in the environment during an ecological crisis are reflected both within the country and internationally. International cooperation in the field of environmental protection has further expanded and acquired a global character [1].

There are two forms of such cooperation: inter-governmental agreements and conventions on environmental protection and national use of natural resources; participation in the work of international nature protection organizations. Interstate Agreements and Conventions are concluded, above all, between states with similar physical and geographical conditions and common borders. The United Nations (UN) system is working hard on international cooperation in the field of environmental protection.

From the earliest days of the United Nations, environmental protection has been one of the organization's practical tasks. In 1949, the first UN action in this area was held in Lake Saks, USA.

Although the technical and economic impact of man on nature and its resources to meet the material and cultural needs of the population was initially primitive, later it became more intense as a result of the intervention of scientific and technological progress in our lives. The development of technical progress, the satisfaction of the need for means of production, consumer goods, cultural and household goods accelerates the use of natural resources, especially minerals. The irrational use of natural resources prematurely depletes resources, slows down the process of self-healing within the framework of natural processes, and creates favorable conditions for the formation of ecological crises in the environment. The high concentration of production leads to the release of waste that is considered harmful to the environment, which leads to a rapid increase in environmental tension in industrial centers. Mechanized, chemicalized agricultural and industrial enterprises annually emit more than 1 million tons of soot, lead, zinc, sulfur, carbon monoxide and other substances into the air [2,3]. Until 1995, the country annually allocated about 170-180 million manats (prices in 1990) for the protection of the environment, polluted by various industrial, transport and household waste. These funds do not amount to even one percent of the damage to environmental, social and economic development in the process of nature management. Such "protection" of nature and the environment is similar to the treatment of a seriously ill patient in intensive care without a medical history. It should also be noted that the amount of marginal waters discharged into the Caspian Sea from large cities and towns on the Absheron Peninsula is many times higher than the norm. Pollutants from natural sources are often short-lived. Higher pollutants are generated in human-related production processes. This situation has led to a fundamental change in the composition of industrial waste and a new quality of air pollution. As a result, dust of heavy and rare elements and synthetic compounds entered the atmosphere.

Even during the development of Asian culture and the middle Ages, people realized that the use of natural resources, in addition to obtaining material benefits, has a negative impact on the environment. In a number of documents discovered during the development of ancient Babylon, Egypt, Rome, Central Asia, the Caucasus, the Kiev-Russian culture, mention is made of limiting the use of biological resources. Two thousand

years ago, China and India struggled with deforestation. In China and Egypt, measures to combat the erosion of fertile lands through government decisions and public initiatives were widely discussed. A person's perception of ecology, respect for certain natural resources stems from his general scientific knowledge, production, professional experience and needs. In this sense, we find a number of valuable information in ancient Egyptian, Indian and European writings. In the Indian epics Mahabharata and Ramayana BC, we meet ideas about changing the quantity and quality of a number of wild animals, a ban on killing female animals [4]. These sagas contain interesting information about the lifestyle and habits of 50 animal species. Although it may seem naive to us now, the ancient authors were able to correctly explain the events that took place in nature and the connections within the living world.

Introduction of the main text. Mankind, as a living being, is inextricably linked with the material and energy processes occurring in the biosphere of the Earth's geological crust. In terms of the mass of living things, a very small part of the biosphere is about 0.25% [5]. It is concentrated on land, in water bodies, in the atmosphere in the form of a thin layer. The process of evolution applies only to living organisms. According to V.I. Vernadsky, a living organism performs biogeochemical functions in the biosphere. The main purpose of environmental protection is to study the impact of various factors, primarily anthropogenic factors, on the elements of the biosphere. Mankind is becoming more and more convinced that the Earth is a unique creation with its own biosphere and living beings. At present, world science and humanity are watching with great excitement dangerous events that can cause possible catastrophes for this unique creation of the planet Earth. These catastrophic events are due to profound changes in the industrial and agricultural activities of modern man, who is considered the most honorable in the world. Human activity primarily has a strong impact on the atmosphere, which leads to catastrophic changes in ecosystems. The more nature is polluted, the less effective is the protection and preservation of the body from xenobiotics. The science of genetics has proven that environmental pollution with toxic and harmful substances has an extremely negative effect on the genetic program of living beings, especially the person himself, and leads to the development of many diseases. For this reason, with the further intensification of the "production" of biological products, priority should be given to environmental problems and the maintenance of optimal living conditions should be planned as much as possible.

The attitude of human society towards nature has changed from time to time. In the beginning, nature was only a source of food for man, and man remained indifferent to the fate of nature. The scientific and cultural achievements of man during the period of 40-50 thousand years of civilization were taken from nature, and all the shortcomings that he has encountered so far have been the result of his mistreatment of nature. Man is the only living being that is trying to completely change the environment. All living things conform to the laws of nature. Only man breaks the laws of nature and tries to completely change them in accordance with his infinite

needs. A person's "successes" in this area are actually his failures. Man's greed to alienate and "conquer" nature has led to the fact that environmental collapse, which is now more dangerous than nuclear weapons, cannot be ruled out.

The main goals and objectives of ecology in our time are to discover the interactions and relationships of anthropogenic ecosystems with nature. The study of ecosystems allows you to determine the volume of metabolism and energy conversion. Man-made productive ecosystems are important in comparison with energy populations and biocenoses. In the conditions of the modern development of science and technology, population growth, the interaction of nature and society has become a universal problem. Raising the material and cultural standard of living of people, increasing the production of material goods raises the question of the efficient use of natural resources. The impact on nature as a result of the activities of people armed with technology and energy is so great that its negative factors can be compared with the strength of many impacts in geological periods.

Efficient use of natural resources and environmental protection have been at the center of attention of the world community over the past hundred years. After the Second World War, under the influence of public opinion, many states took important measures and decisions in this regard. It should be noted that nature conservation has been an important issue since the beginning of the 20th century. The VII International Zoological Congress in Graz (Austria) in 1910 and the International Conference on Nature Conservation in Bern in 1913, in addition to issues of practical importance, set a number of important tasks for the conservation and protection of natural resources for future generations [6].

In the last 45-50 years, the global public exchange of views on environmental issues has become more and more widespread. At the suggestion of most countries, the International Conference on the Protection of the Biosphere and its Resources, held in Paris in 1968 under the auspices of UNESCO, the Congress of the Economic Commission for Europe on Environmental Protection in Prague in 1971, and in recent years the United Nations Conference on Environmental Protection environments have set important tasks for society in the field of nature protection.

A great influence on the organization of environmental protection, the functioning of the program of the UN Conference on Human Protection in 1972, the implementation of a number of proposals of the UN General Assembly, such as the Declaration on Security and Cooperation in Europe (1975) was.

In developed countries, such as North America, Western Europe, Japan and a number of CIS countries, environmental protection is more stringent. They have done important work in the fight against pollution of transit rivers for the cleanliness of the environment along the borders of these countries. The first international conference on nature conservation took place in 1913 in Bern, Switzerland [7,8]. Representatives of 17 countries took part in the conference at the invitation of Switzerland. These were Austria, Germany, USA, Argentina, Belgium, Great Britain, Denmark, Sweden, Switzerland, Spain, Italy, Hungary, the Netherlands,

Norway, Portugal, Russia, and France. The focus of the conference was on the collection and publication of information on the use of natural resources and nature protection. The Swiss scientist Paul Sarasin delivered the main lecture at the conference. He spoke about the destruction of nature by individual states and raised the question of ways to prevent the rapid destruction of animals living in the seas, oceans and on land. It should be noted that the activities of the seven UN specialized councils are directly related to environmental issues. They put forward plans and measures to eliminate a number of negative symptoms caused by the impact of people armed with equipment on nature. Since its inception, ie since 1945, UNESCO has been the most famous and advanced center for monitoring cooperation in the field of environmental protection and the implementation of organizational measures [9, 10]. Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that the historical role of ecology in human life is an indisputable fact from the moment of the existence of the human race to the last moments of the existence of humanity. Thus, a person interacts with the environment from the day of his existence in the world, and as a result of this interaction, his negative and positive (in most cases this impact is considered the most negative) manifestation in any form in the environment does not necessarily manifest itself.

Conclusion. According to the research results, it should be noted that it is better to prevent the occurrence of environmental problems with the help of preventive measures than to think about solutions to environmental problems caused by any anthropogenic activity in the field of environmental protection and rational use of natural resources.

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